

DATA NOTE

ERGA-BGE reference genome of the Azores Bullfinch - *Pyrrhula murina* Godman, 1866: an IUCN Vulnerable Species endemic to a single island in the Azores Archipelago (Portugal)

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

Pyrrhula murina's reference genome will substantially enhance the current monitoring of genetic diversity and population viability and will allow us to understand the effective population size trends throughout time and recent bottlenecks and population expansions. A total of 42 contiguous chromosomal pseudomolecules were assembled from the genome sequence. This chromosome-level assembly encompasses 1.2 Gb, composed of 65 contigs and 60 scaffolds, with contig and scaffold N50 values of 64.8 Mb and 76 Mb, respectively.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
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(revision)		
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version 2		
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version 3

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Pyrrhula murina, Fringillidae family, Azores Bullfinch, genome assembly, European Reference Genome Atlas, Biodiversity Genomics Europe, Earth Biogenome Project

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

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Author roles: **Lopes RJ:** Investigation, Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Böhne A:** Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Marcussen T:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Oomen RA:** Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Struck TH:** Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Aguilera L:** Investigation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Gut M:** Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Câmara Ferreira F:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Review & Editing; **Cruz F:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Review & Editing; **Gómez-Garrido J:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Review & Editing; **Alioto TS:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Monteiro R:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

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Introduction

The Azores Bullfinch, *Pyrrhula murina* Godman, 1866, is restricted to a small area that includes native laurel forest, in the east of the largest island (São Miguel) of the Azores archipelago. It is thought to have diverged from its nearest sister species more than 1 MYA (Töpfer *et al.*, 2011).

By the late 19th/early 20th century, the Azores Bullfinch was already very rare and restricted to the higher mountain valleys in the east of São Miguel island (Aubrecht, 2000). It was rediscovered only in the last century, and numbers have increased due to conservation efforts to protect this species and its main habitat. Its current population size is estimated at around 1000 individuals (Ceia *et al.*, 2011; Costa *et al.*, 2023; Gil *et al.*, 2016), and its conservation status has been down-listed from “Critically Endangered” to “Vulnerable” on the IUCN Red List, as the population size is considered to be stable (BirdLife International, 2021).

It is one of the few endemic bird species that is strongly connected to the last remnants of the Laurel Forest in the Azores, providing key ecological services for the sustainability of these habitats.

This kind of high-quality reference genome will allow us to enhance our knowledge on the long-term viability of this small population, informing us about the impact of the multiple bottlenecks on its genetic diversity and also on the current and future evolution of this population. Of particular importance for its viability, is the fact that, along with his sister species, the Eurasian Bullfinch, *Pyrrhula pyrrhula*, they have relatively small and possibly neotenus sperm, an ancestral trait that evolved before the two taxa diverged (Lifjeld *et al.*, 2013).

The generation of this reference resource was coordinated by the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) initiative’s Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) project, supporting ERGA’s aims of promoting transnational cooperation to promote advances in the application of genomics technologies to protect and restore biodiversity (Mazzoni *et al.*, 2023).

Materials & methods

ERGA’s sequencing strategy includes Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) and/or Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) for long-read sequencing, along with Hi-C sequencing for chromosomal architecture, Illumina Paired-End (PE) for polishing (i.e. recommended for ONT-only assemblies), and RNA sequencing for transcriptomic profiling, to facilitate genome assembly and annotation.

Sample and sampling information

On November 27, 2023, a female adult (determined based on genetic sexing) of *Pyrrhula murina* was sampled and identified by Ricardo Jorge Lopes. The specimen was caught using mist-nets in a woodland area in Salto do Cavallo, São Miguel island, in the Azores archipelago, Portugal.

This species is unmistakable, being the sole representative of this Genus in the Azores Archipelago.

Sampling was performed under permit 119/2023/DRAAC, from the Regional Directorate for the Environment and Climate Action, of the Azores Government, and under the Internationally Recognized Compliance certificate CCIR-RAA/2023/65. The specimen’s blood samples were snap-frozen immediately after harvesting and stored in liquid nitrogen until DNA extraction.

Vouchering information

An electronic voucher image of the sequenced individual is available from ERGA’s EBI BioImageArchive dataset www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/bioimages/studies/S-BIAD1012?query=ERGA under accession ID SAMEA115966740.

A frozen reference blood sample from the sequenced individual was deposited at MUHNAC (National Museum of Natural History and Science of the University of Lisbon), under the voucher ID C67972_Blood_05.

Genetic information

The estimated genome size, based on ancestral taxa, is 1.33 Gb, while the estimation based on reads kmer profiling is 1.08 Gb. This is a diploid genome with a haploid number of 39 chromosomes ($2n = 78$), including Z and W sex chromosomes in females. All information for this species was retrieved from Genomes on a Tree (Challis *et al.*, 2023).

DNA/RNA processing

DNA was extracted from blood using the Blood & Cell Culture DNA Midi Kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer’s instructions. DNA quantification was performed using a Qubit dsDNA BR Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and DNA integrity was assessed using a Genomic DNA 165 Kb Kit (Agilent) on the Femto Pulse system (Agilent). The DNA was stored at +4 °C until used.

RNA was extracted from blood using an RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer’s instructions. RNA quantification was performed using the Qubit RNA BR kit, and RNA integrity was assessed using a Bioanalyzer 2100 system (Agilent) RNA 6000 Nano Kit (Agilent). The RNA was stored at -80 °C until used.

Library preparation and sequencing

For long-read whole genome sequencing, a library was prepared using the SQK-LSK114 Kit (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, ONT), which was then sequenced on a PromethION 24 A Series instrument (ONT). A short-read whole-genome sequencing library was prepared using the KAPA Hyper Prep Kit (Roche).

A Hi-C library was prepared from blood using the Dovetail Omni-C Kit (Cantata Bio), followed by the KAPA Hyper Prep Kit for Illumina sequencing (Roche).

The RNA library was prepared using the KAPA mRNA Hyper prep kit (Roche). The short-read libraries were sequenced on a NovaSeq 6000 instrument (Illumina).

In total, 100x Oxford Nanopore, 99x Illumina WGS shotgun, and 79x HiC data were sequenced to generate the assembly.

Genome assembly methods

The genome was assembled using the CNAG CLAWS pipeline v2.2.0 (Gomez-Garrido, 2024). Briefly, reads were pre-processed for quality and length using Trim Galore v0.6.7 and Filtlong v0.2.1, and initial contigs were assembled using NextDenovo v2.5.0, followed by polishing of the assembled contigs using HyPo v1.0.3, removal of retained haplotigs using purge-dups v1.2.6 and scaffolding with YaHS v1.2a. Finally, assembled scaffolds were curated via manual inspection using Pretext v0.2.5 with the Rapid Curation Toolkit (https://gitlab.com/wtsi-grit/rapid-curation) to remove any false joins and incorporate any sequences not automatically scaffolded into their respective locations in the chromosomal

pseudomolecules (or super-scaffolds). The blobtoolkit nextflow pipeline v0.6.0 (https://pipelines.tol.sanger.ac.uk/blobtoolkit/0.6.0/usage) confirmed the absence of contaminants. Finally, the mitochondrial genome was assembled as a single circular contig of 16,836 bp using the FOAM pipeline v0.5 (https://github.com/cnag-aat/FOAM) and included in the released assembly (GCA_965183895.1). Summary analysis of the released assembly was performed using the ERGA-BGE Genome Report ASM Galaxy workflow (De Panis, 2024a).

Results

Genome assembly

The genome assembly has a total length of 1,163,884,374 bp in 61 scaffolds, including the mitogenome (Figure 1 and Figure 2), with a GC content of 43.29%. It features a contig N50 of 64,819,875 bp (L50=6) and a scaffold N50 of 76,036,967 bp (L50=6). There are 5 gaps, totaling 1,000 kb in cumulative size. The single-copy gene content analysis using the aves_odb10 database with BUSCO (Manni et al., 2021) resulted in 96.9% completeness (96.3% single and 0.6%

Figure 1. Snail plot summary of assembly statistics. The main plot is divided into 1,000 size-ordered bins around the circumference, with each bin representing 0.1% of the 1,163,884,374bp assembly, including the mitochondrial genome. The distribution of sequence lengths is shown in dark grey, with the plot radius scaled to the longest sequence present in the assembly (155 Mb bp, shown in red). Orange and pale-orange arcs show the scaffold N50 and N90 sequence lengths (76,036,967 and 12,418,366 bp), respectively. The pale grey spiral shows the cumulative sequence count on a log-scale, with white scale lines showing successive orders of magnitude. The blue and pale-blue area around the outside of the plot shows the distribution of GC, AT, and N percentages in the same bins as the inner plot. A summary of complete, fragmented, duplicated, and missing BUSCO genes found in the assembled genome from the avian database (odb10) is shown on the top right.

Figure 2. Hi-C contact map showing spatial interactions between regions of the genome. The diagonal corresponds to intra-chromosomal contacts, depicting chromosome boundaries. The frequency of contacts is shown on a logarithmic heatmap scale. Hi-C matrix bins were merged into a 150 kb bin size for plotting. Due to space constraints on the axes, only the GenBank names of the 13th largest autosomes and the sex chromosomes are shown.

duplicated). 98.6% of reads k-mers were present in the assembly, and the assembly has a base accuracy Quality Value (QV) of 52.6 as calculated by Merqury (Rhie *et al.*, 2020).

Data availability

Pyrrhula murina and the related genomic study were assigned to Tree of Life ID (ToLID) ‘bPyrMur1’, and all sample, sequence, and assembly information are available under the umbrella BioProject PRJEB86373 from <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86373>. The sample information is available at the following BioSample accessions: SAMEA115966741 and SAMEA115966742. The genome assembly is accessible from ENA under accession number GCA_965183895.

Sequencing data produced as part of this project are available from ENA at the following accessions: ERX14064180, ERX14064181, and ERX14064182. Documentation related to the genome assembly and curation can be found in the ERGA Assembly Report (EAR) document available at https://github.com/ERGA-consortium/EARs/tree/main/Assembly_Reports/Pyrrhula_murina/bPyrMur1. The mitochondrial genome was assembled into a single circular contig using the FOAM pipeline v0.5 (<https://github.com/cnag-aat/FOAM>). Further details

and data about the project are hosted on the ERGA portal at https://portal.erga-biodiversity.eu/data_portal/928672.

Author contributions

RJL coordinated the project, collected the species, identified the species, sampled and preserved biological material and provided metadata, RM, TM, RAO, THS, and AsB provided sampling and metadata support and management, LA and MG extracted DNA, prepared libraries, and performed sequencing, FCF, JGG and FC performed genome assembly and curation under the supervision of TA, RM generated the analysis and report. All authors contributed to the writing, review, and editing of this genome note and read and approved the final version.

Acknowledgements

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Version 1

Reviewer Report 12 September 2025

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Annabel Whibley

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Lopes and colleagues describe the generation of a reference genome assembly for the Azores Bullfinch, *Pyrrhula murina*, a species classified as Vulnerable by the IUCN. The quality of the genome is high, with >96% BUSCO completeness and a base-level accuracy of 52.6QV. The assembly has been scaffolded into chromosomal pseudomolecules, although no comment is made on the discrepancy between the 42 pseudochromosomes recovered and the expected $2n=78$ nor to whether any of the scaffolds/contigs remain unlinked to chromosomes.

The assembly and supporting data have been publicly released and the accession links are active. The authors describe obtaining RNA sequencing data but an annotation is not provided here.

While the manuscript is generally well-structured and is close to the Data Note template used by the Darwin Tree of Life consortium, there are notable gaps in the reporting of methods and important metadata details. For example, the methods section presents a genome size estimate from kmer analysis without noting how this method was obtained (GenomeScope2 with a kmer length of X?). The versions of software used are not always reported and key parameters are sometimes omitted. What are the parameters used to filter the sequencing reads? What are the properties (beyond coverage) of the ONT libraries? The flow cell type (R10.4.1) should probably be reported for the ONT sequencing along with the library type. Methods reporting manual curation would typically also give an indication of the number and type of interventions.

Some of the language is a little informal. For example, the opening of the abstract with a possessive rather than "The reference genome of..." is unusual. And "This kind of high-quality..." in the introduction is vague.

This sentence needs revision: "Of particular importance for its viability, is the fact that, along with his sister species, the Eurasian Bullfinch, *Pyrrhula pyrrhula*, they have relatively small and possibly neotenous sperm, an ancestral trait that evolved before the two taxa diverged (Lifjeld et al.,

2013).” I would suggest : Of particular importance for **the viability of the species**, is the fact that *Pyrrhula murina*, along with a sister species, the Eurasian Bullfinch, *Pyrrhula pyrrhula*, have relatively small and possibly neotenus sperm, an ancestral trait that evolved before the two taxa diverged (Lifjeld et al., 2013).”

The introduction of the methods describes RNA sequencing data without noting the sequencing type and states that it is used to facilitate genome assembly and annotation, with scant methodological evidence that the RNA dataset has informed the assembly generation.

The latitude and longitude co-ordinates for the collection site should be included.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Genomics, Bioinformatics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 29 Jan 2026

Rita Monteiro

We thank the reviewer for their comments. We have addressed all of them as following:

1. The discrepancy between the previously reported of 39 pseudochromosomes ($2n=78$) and the 42 pseudochromosomes recovered in our assembly can be explained by differences in how the chromosome number was inferred. The number $2n=78$ pseudochromosomes was obtained from GOAT, which estimates it based on comparative karyotype data from ancestral taxa (as indicated in the main text) rather than direct cytogenetic observation for this species. We have now modified the text to clarify this point better. In contrast, our assembly provides species specific evidence, revealing 40 pairs of autosomes plus two sex chromosomes. In addition, 11 scaffolds remain unplaced in the current assembly.
2. As noted in our response to the other reviewer, a full genome annotation for this species is not yet available: it is currently being generated and will be released as

soon as completed.

3. We thank the reviewer for pointing this out. As suggested we have now included the genome size estimation method - GenomeScope2 with a k-mer length of 21. In addition, we have also included the corresponding software versions BUSCO v5.5.0 and Merqury v1.3, as also suggested by the other reviewer. Furthermore, we now report the number and kind of interventions made during manual curation.
4. We have modified the highlighted examples to improve clarity and formality.
5. Modified accordingly.
6. We have clarified the text, separating the RNA-seq data production from the rest of the data, highlighting that the purpose of its production is to aid future annotation efforts. We include transcriptomic data for the purpose of efficiency. Collecting RNA from the same specimen (or from different specimens) during the same sampling event is important and saves time, effort and costs when it comes to annotation of the reference genomes produced. The annotation step is downstream of the assembly and can take substantially more time, thus we release the assemblies as soon as possible and decouple the annotation step from necessary inclusion in the Genome Note.
7. All relevant metadata, including the collection site and coordinates are available under the umbrella BioProject PRJEB86373 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86373>) and in the ERGA portal (https://portal.erga-biodiversity.eu/data_portal/928672). Both links are included in the main text.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

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Luke W Silver

University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia

Reviewer Comments

The authors generate a draft genome for the Azores Bullfinch, a IUCN Vulnerably listed species, using ONT, HiC and Illumina data. Overall the methods of genome assembly and quality checking are sound and will provide a useful resource, however, there are a few details which would improve the data note.

Include sequencing technology used in the Abstract

Where is the Azores archipelago located in wider context – i.e. XX km west of Portugal in the Atlantic Ocean or include a figure of the location, maybe a panel with an image of the Azores Bullfinch

“As a result of” instead of “due to”

“A high quality..” instead of “this kind of...”

“Sequencing” instead of “used”

What type of RNA short read libraries – 150bp paired end?

How many reads were generated by RNA sequencing?

Say which data type was used in each of the steps – i.e. scaffolding using HiC data with YaHS...

Some details of the assembly summary analysis is needed, such as the which version of BUSCO and Merqury are used in this workflow?

Was any repeat identification undertaken?

Which scaffold was identified as the mitochondrial genome?

Method details are needed for how the sex scaffolds were identified

Were the RNA seq reads used for any analysis or just generated for ENA submission?

If there are any other genomes for closely related species is it expected that there are 13 macrochromosomes and then microchromosomes or is the number of macrochromosomes unknown?

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Genome assembly, genetic diversity

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 29 Jan 2026

Rita Monteiro

We thank the reviewer for their comments. We have addressed all of them as following:

1. Added to the Abstract
2. We included a new figure (Figure 1) that shows the wider spatial context in relation to the nearest continental grounds, and the location of the Azores Bullfinch range inside

- the São Miguel Island. We also include a photo of the Azores Bullfinch.
3. Modified accordingly.
 4. Modified accordingly.
 5. Modified accordingly.
 6. Were produced 150bp paired end RNA libraries. This information was added to the main text.
 7. 91MR were generated, added to the text.
 8. We assembled contigs from ONT data with Hi-C for phasing. We scaffolded with YaHS using Hi-C data. K-mer counts for estimating genome size, QV and k-mer completeness were performed on the combined set of Illumina WGS and filtered ONT reads. This information was added to the text.
 9. For the assembly summary analysis we used BUSCO v5.5.0 and Merquy v1.3. This information was added to the main text.
 10. Yes, repeats were identified using RepeatMasker (Smit, AFA, Hubley, R & Green, P., 2013-2015), (version 4.0.5 with parameters -nolow -engine "RMBlast"), dustmasker (Morgulis, A., et al., 2006), and tandem repeat finder, TRF (Benson, G., 1999). In addition to the Repbase (Bao, W., et al, 2015) library, where available, a custom repeat library is used with RepeatMasker. Custom libraries are created using RepeatModeler2 (Flynn, J.M., 2020)
 11. The mitochondrial genome corresponds to chr OZ239036.1. This was added to the main text.
 12. We have added the following text to the methods:
"The sex chromosomes were identified by sequencing coverage. Assignment of Z and W chromosomes was according to conservation of length: bPyrMur chrZ (OZ238997.1: 86793913 bp) vs. bGalGal chrZ (CM028522.1: 86044486 bp). Whole genome alignment against GRCg7b (GCA_016699485.1) confirmed these assignments."
 13. As indicated, RNA sequencing was performed for transcriptome profiling with the primary aim of supporting genome assembly and annotation. Although a full genome annotation for this species is not yet available, it is currently being generated and will be released as soon as it becomes available.
 14. We did not include any information with respect to macro- vs. microchromosomes as there is some debate in the literature as to the length threshold (35 Mb? 30? 20 Mb?). It seems that the categorization is done by karyotyping and varies from one bird species to the next. For *P. murina*, the clearest size break occurs between about 23 and 28 Mb. It has 10 autosomes and the Z and W that are longer than 28 Mb and the rest (30 autosomes) are shorter than 23 Mb, the shortest being about 3.5 Mb. We have added this information to the text but avoid the macro- micro- labels.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.